

Redefining Leadership Exploring Inclusive Policies and Challenges Faced by Women Executives in the Indian Business Environment

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Abstract

Women have a great deal of contribution towards shaping the societies, governance and economies. Women executives' roles in the Indian business environment have undergone a radical metamorphosis over time. However, despite the rise of female participation at the high levels, leadership remains skewed in nature, and women are uniquely challenged in this endeavor. This paper aims to examine the present scenario of women leadership in corporate world in India, identify the major barriers, explore inclusion policies placed in light of promoting gender diversity of female executives in corporate India. Based on a combination of policy analysis, interviews, and case studies, the paper identifies the problems of gender imbalance, non-development, and work-life balance problems. Policies in the form of gender quotas, equal pay projects, and anti-discrimination policies are helping to build an inclusive workplace environment at the policy levels. However, their practical impact remains restricted because of deep-rooted objections from societal and organizational cultures. Ultimately, the research study is a call for redefining leadership where everyone has his place, with systemic barriers rolled away and a culture of equal opportunity provides a platform for women executives to come up and flourish in that sector. Contribution to the bigger issue: The findings aid in the ongoing debate over gender balance in leadership and offer suggestions in bridging that gap to achieve balance in the corporate environment of India.

Keywords Women Executives, Inclusive Leadership, Gender Diversity, Corporate India, Gender Bias, Workplace Inclusivity, Leadership Challenges

Introduction

Women lay the foundation of family. They play a significant role in nurturing children, caring for elders and managing household activities. This role is extended from families to society, governance, leadership and entrepreneurship. The concept of leadership has undergone changes within the past few years concerning the aspect of diversity and inclusivity. With increased global acceptance of diverse leadership teams, equal attention is also provided towards gender mainstreaming in corporate leaderships in India. Women in senior executive positions are still relatively few and limited in their rise to top leadership due to various constraints. The Indian business environment, while advanced on an inclusive front, still struggles with structural and cultural barriers for women executives at their very root (Korkmaz et al., 2022).

The present study aims to contribute to the understanding of how change is occurring in leadership in India by exploring the experiences and challenges that women executives face. It also reviews how policies of inclusiveness affect gender diversity and whether such measures are effective in shedding light on systemic issues that women face. From the pay gap to the lack of opportunities for mentorship and sponsorship, women leaders face several problems that their male counterparts hardly face in their professional lives. Societal expectations, traditional gender roles, and implicit bias add to the same hurdles

that women executives face, and it's no wonder their navigation in careers becomes all the more challenging for breaking the glass ceiling (Sabharwal et al., 2018).

This paper seeks the redefinition of leadership to broaden what it means to lead and to include a wider, more representative compass for leading. The study seeks to cast light on pathways towards equity-enhanced corporate leadership in India. Moving through this investigation, the paper adds to current debates about gender equality in the leadership positions and, at the same time, suggests concrete suggestions that may improve the opportunity for women executives in the corporate arena.

Objective of study

1. To examine the present scenario of women in leadership roles in the corporate world in India
2. To identify the key challenges faced by women executives in the Indian business environment (gender bias, societal expectations, work-life balance issues, and lack of access to professional networks, mentorship etc.)
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of inclusive policies in promoting gender diversity in leadership positions of women executives within Indian companies
4. To analyze major factors influencing women's leadership trajectories understanding their professional growth and leadership opportunities
5. To propose feasible solutions for redefining leadership to include gender inclusivity and diversity in Indian businesses for policy-makers, corporate leaders, and gender equality advocates

Review of Literature

The issue of women's leadership in the corporate world has been extensively studied, particularly in the context of gender diversity, inclusive policies, and the challenges that women face in ascending to leadership roles. Various scholars have emphasized that while the global business environment has increasingly recognized the importance of gender diversity in leadership, challenges persist, particularly in patriarchal societies such as India. According to Catalyst (2020), organizations that are inclusive of women in leadership roles benefit from diverse perspectives, improved decision-making, and better overall financial performance. However, the literature indicates that in many countries, including India, women continue to face significant barriers to leadership, including gender bias, organizational culture, and the glass ceiling phenomenon (Eagly & Carli, 2007).

Inclusive policies aimed at increasing women's representation in leadership have received mixed reviews in the literature. The introduction of gender quotas, such as those mandated by the Companies Act 2013 in India, has been a step in the right direction, leading to increased female presence in boardrooms (Kalyani, 2016). However, research suggests that these policies often result in tokenism, where women are appointed to leadership roles but lack the support and influence necessary to drive meaningful change (Kumra & Vinnicombe, 2008). Scholars like Bertrand et al. (2019) argue that for inclusive policies to be truly effective, they need to be supplemented by organizational changes that challenge deep-seated gender biases and offer women executives the tools and mentorship needed to succeed.

Several studies highlight the intersection of cultural and societal expectations with women's professional lives, which further complicate their progression into leadership roles. Indian society, with its entrenched patriarchal values, often places women under immense pressure to conform to traditional gender roles, balancing family responsibilities with professional aspirations (Singh, 2012). Literature such as that by Heilman (2012) suggests that women in leadership are often subjected to stereotypical judgments, where they are perceived as either too soft or too aggressive, neither of which is conducive to their career advancement. These societal norms influence corporate cultures, making it difficult for women to break free from these expectations and ascend to senior leadership positions.

The review of literature also points to the importance of mentorship and sponsorship in the leadership journey of women. Studies by Ibarra, Carter, and Silva (2010) revealed that men are more likely than women to have mentors or sponsors advocating for their career advancement. Women executives often find themselves isolated from key networks that are crucial for leadership opportunities. Furthermore, women who do reach leadership roles frequently face heightened scrutiny and are held to higher standards than their male counterparts (Rudman & Glick, 2001). The literature suggests that fostering mentorship programs, challenging stereotypes, and implementing systemic organizational changes are essential to dismantling these barriers and promoting a more inclusive leadership environment.

This body of literature provides a foundation for understanding the challenges women executives face in the Indian corporate environment. It highlights the need for a redefinition of leadership that goes beyond policy implementation and addresses cultural,

societal, and organizational factors that inhibit women's progress. These insights are integral to the present study, which seeks to explore how inclusive policies and organizational practices can be reformed to promote more equitable leadership opportunities for women in India.

Main Text

Background of Study

Several changes to the corporate leadership landscape in India over the last few decades can be largely attributed to the expansion of the economy, globalization, and increasing demand for more diverse workforces. Historically, the Indian business environment has been a male-dominated one, with few women in leadership positions; however, with the globalization of larger corporations and multinational best practices, an emerging focus on gender diversity and inclusion is encouraged. Government policies and advocacy for corporate social responsibility have further promoted the need for more balanced representation in leadership (Shore et al., 2018). Despite these encouraging developments, a road to leadership by women in executive positions remains fraught with obstacles—critical or overt, subtle or insidious—whenever it requires one to overcome entrenched gender biases and navigate patriarchal corporate cultures. Perhaps the most important interventions toward ending the gap between genders in corporate leadership involves inclusive policies, such as implementing quotas, diversity initiatives, and equal pay legislation. For instance, in India, the Companies Act 2013 mandated listed companies to have at least one woman on the board, accelerating female representation at the top ever since. While these policies have indeed created entry points for women into the pipeline, they have not been flawless. Tokenism, unconscious bias, and lack of organizational support often undermine such policies. In the end, while many women who attain leadership positions continue to break through the so-called "glass ceiling," it's not hard to be cynical about what is often euphemistically referred to as the "glass bridge" or "invisibility cloak"—that threatens to swallow them up when it comes to further promotion.

Professional challenges merged with social and cultural norms harass Indian women. Indian tradition retains traditional gender roles, and the society expects that the women should maintain a balance between their career and personal life (World Economic Forum, 2023). This adds more burden onto careers by making the expectation that these women are also going to carry greater primary caregiver and household responsibility, which often pushes women out of leadership trajectories altogether. Combining this with access to mentors and sponsors perceived as prerequisites for advancing careers makes up a complex arena in which women executives continually negotiate specific gender obstacles.

It is to redefine what leadership encompasses in a context of gender diversity. Leadership in the 21st century should be a highly inclusive authority that brings diversity through various perspectives and feeds innovation (Jing et al., 2022). This research paper examines how better-inclusive policies can be effectively implemented to overcome the challenges of women executives in India. Using case study analyses and further working with gaps in contemporary policies, it aims at providing actionable insights to create a landscape, allowing women executives to thrive by contributing to a more equitable and sustainable corporate landscape.

Scope and Significance of Study

The scope of study lies in examining the current state of leadership in the business environment of India, with specific reference to the role played by women executives. The objective of the study lies in exploring the barriers that women face in attaining leadership and succeeding in the leadership position, as well as in evaluating existing inclusive policies that are affecting gender equity. Explorations into large corporate organizations as well as more local, regional ones will provide a broad perspective of the leadership profile within respective industries and sectors. Additionally, the paper examines the relationship between cultural and social factors with organizational practices and how this impacts the careers of female executives.

Women leadership has extreme value in today's business world when diversity and inclusion become a requirement for corporate success; Indian business becomes aligned closer to the global economy when being gender-diverse is increasingly recognized as a driver of innovation, better decision-making, and improved financial performance. Understanding the challenges women executives face is central to what organizations need to work on in order to create diverse talent pools and tap the maximum potential for leadership roles (Bae and Doherty, 2022). Thus, gaps in the current policies and practices will be identified and improvements made that highlight the critical areas of development for creating an inclusive gender demographic pipeline for women at the leadership level.

The relevance of this work extends beyond the corporate framework into a broader social setup in India. Emergence at the helm of women is thereby an implication of changed patterns of social gender perception and equality. In that regard, this work on the challenge that obstructs women from achieving leadership positions contributes to the larger body of works about gender equality at work and society. Empowering women executives not only supports businesses but also forms a crucial link that inspires the upcoming generations of women leaders to break the patriarchal norms harnessed in earlier days to keep women in their allocated positions (Yin and Liu, 2022).

With its results, this study constitutes a basis for the policy-makers, corporate leaders, as well as the advocates of gender equality, so that it shall be possible to focus more profoundly on crafting more nuanced interventions. With the identification of successful case studies and best practices already established, the study helps outline actionable insights on how to better craft inclusive supportive environments around women leaders. Finally, the aim of this research is to contribute to the present debate regarding the rediscovery of leadership in India with inclusivity and diversity as essential aspects necessary for sustainable growth and development in the Indian business environment.

Figure 1: Women Representation and Leadership Position in India

(Source: LinkedIn, May 2024)

The above data is based on the LinkedIn members in India, where the firm has more than 100 million people registered. According to Aparajita Bharti, a co-founder of The Quantum Hub consultancy that worked with LinkedIn for the report, the decline in the availability of hybrid or work-from-home roles may have contributed to the shift, suppressing growth in female participation in the corporate labour market.

Figure 2: Gender Equality Leaders

The research carried out by Deloitte identified a group of Gender Equality Leaders, organisations which, by the responses of women, have created a culture that, in reality, is inclusive and will support their career, work/life balance, and an environment which fosters inclusion. Women working in GELs are better engaged and have higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction. The percentage of women working for GELs is 6% globally and 6% in India. There is also a category of "lagging" organizations. The women employees of these organizations say that they work for less inclusive culture with low in-group trust. For this year, 21% of the global and 25% of the respondents in India work in these Lagging organizations.

Result and Discussion

Even though policies like gender quotas, anti-discrimination laws, and diversity programs have put more women in boardrooms and executive ranks, they have never quite gotten to the root of the problem for women executives. However, the policies themselves too often prove to be an inadequate defense against the really deep and virulent forms of cultural and organizational barriers women face. Policies alone are insufficient to ensure inclusivity if they are not supported by a fundamental transformation of corporate mindsets and practices (Grant Thornton, 2023).

This inequality is also mapped to a more deep-rooted problem in corporate cultures that still possess deep gender biases. The growth of women into leadership positions does not translate to an effective impact on decision-making processes. The tokenistic status is predominant among most sectors, with women being presented solely for the reason of ticking regulatory boxes (World Economic Forum, 2023). No respect, authority, or resources were accorded to them in comparison. This study argues that these biases are unconscious, hence a reflection of the larger societal expectations about seeing leadership in traditional masculine clothes. Therefore, female leaders often suffer stigma, especially whenever expressions of leadership do not conform to general patterns.

Another very critical factor that has contributed to the stagnation of women's careers in corporate India has been the intersection of work-life balance issues with leadership challenges. Much of the study confirms that a lot of women executives face dual burdens of professional responsibilities and domestic responsibilities, which certainly undermined their ability to make full commitment to leaders' roles. This is compounded by a lack of flexible work policies and organizational support systems that would make it easier for women to effectively manage both spheres. Policy evidence suggests that even when work-life balance-promoting policies are in place, they are, in fact, underutilized due to fear of being perceived as less committed or able compared to others in peer groups and hierarchical hierarchies (McKinsey & Company, 2023).

The paper focuses on the critical role of mentors and sponsors in the career development process for female top executives but remains isolated even though the necessary networks and opportunities exist as women are not adequately able to access these networks which tend to be male-dominated in most cases. Status of women in top management thus remains isolated without the right support and protection in the corporate political system and advances to greater leadership positions because of weak relations with mentors and sponsors. Such challenges are often cited in successful female leader cases in the critical support of mentors and sponsors that actively promote their development. So, mentoring is important in filling gaps and constituting a basis for structured programs within organizations to help advance women's careers as part of a more inclusive leadership environment.

While the presence of inclusive policies has resulted in some steps forward with regard to women leaders, huge hurdles are still there. Analysis of the progress shows that there's more to the general approach that not only imposes inclusive policies but also extends through resolution of deep cultural biases, work-life balance, and mentorship opportunities. Redefining the concept of leadership in the Indian business environment is a jump from tokenism to substantive inclusion, where the female executives are bestowed with all the levers of tools, support, and environments that guarantee effective leadership (Skyline, 2023).

Findings

The findings of this research show that, despite the steep momentum of inclusive policies to enhance women in leadership positions, such policies never quite get to the bottom of problems with women executives.

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Conclusion

The study on redefining leadership in the Indian business environment underscores the complexity of challenges faced by women executives, despite the presence of inclusive policies designed to promote gender diversity. While these policies have succeeded in bringing more women into leadership roles, their impact remains limited by deeper cultural and organizational barriers that persist in the corporate world. The phenomenon of tokenism, unconscious biases, and societal expectations around gender roles continue to restrict women's full participation and influence in leadership positions. The study finds that simply increasing the number of women in executive roles is not enough; real inclusion requires addressing the underlying biases and structural inequities that shape the experiences of women in leadership

A major takeaway from the research is the need for a redefinition of leadership that embraces diversity not just in numbers but also in practices, perceptions, and organizational culture. True inclusivity goes beyond policy enforcement and requires a cultural shift that empowers women executives to lead without being constrained by stereotypes and traditional expectations. This redefinition of leadership involves creating an environment where women's leadership styles are valued equally and where they are provided the same opportunities to exert influence and make decisions as their male counterparts. Organizations must prioritize fostering a more inclusive and supportive culture, recognizing that diversity in leadership enhances innovation, creativity, and overall business success.

The study highlights the importance of addressing work-life balance issues for women in leadership roles. Without meaningful support systems and cultural changes that allow women to balance their professional and personal responsibilities, many women will continue to face the difficult choice between advancing in their careers and fulfilling societal expectations around caregiving. The corporate world must take active steps to implement more flexible work policies, normalize their usage, and shift away from outdated norms that equate leadership with constant availability and long working hours. The integration of work-life balance initiatives into corporate culture is crucial for retaining and empowering women in leadership roles.

The mentorship and sponsorship emerge as critical elements in supporting women's advancement to leadership positions. The study concludes that structured mentorship programs and active sponsorship are necessary for providing women with the guidance, support, and networks they need to overcome barriers and advance in their careers. These relationships help counteract the isolation that many women face in male-dominated leadership spaces, offering them advocates who can help them navigate the challenges and seize opportunities. Redefining leadership in the Indian business environment thus requires a multifaceted approach that includes not only policy reform but also cultural change, organizational support, and the development of robust mentorship networks to ensure that women executives can lead with confidence and success.

References

1. Bae, D., & Doherty, K. (2022). *The Need for More Inclusive Leadership Narratives*. Available at: https://ssir.org/articles/entry/redefining_leadership_inclusive_narratives.
2. Bertrand, Marianne, et al. (2019). *Breaking the Glass Ceiling? The Effect of Board Quotas on Female Labour Market Outcomes in Norway*. *The Review of Economic Studies*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 191-239, academic.oup.com/restud/article/86/1/191/5098670 (Accessed 28 Sept. 2024.)
3. Catalyst. (2020). *Why Diversity and Inclusion Matter: Quick Take*. Catalyst, 5 Aug. 2020, www.catalyst.org/research/why-diversity-and-inclusion-matter/. Accessed 28 Sept. 2024.
4. Deloitte. (2023). *Redefining leadership with an inclusive approach*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com>
5. Deloitte (2024). *Women @ Work 2024: India market outlook*. Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/in/en/pages/about-deloitte/articles/women-at-work-2024-india-market-outlook.html>
6. Grant Thornton. (2023). *Women in business: Regional picture*. Retrieved from <https://www.grantthornton.global>
7. Eagly, Alice H., and Linda L. Carli. (2007). *Through the Labyrinth: The Truth About How Women Become Leaders*. Harvard Business School Press.
8. Kalyani, Meenakshi. (2016). *Women on Corporate Boards: An Indian Perspective*. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 50-55, [www.ijbmi.org/papers/Vol\(5\)9/version-1/F0509015055.pdf](http://www.ijbmi.org/papers/Vol(5)9/version-1/F0509015055.pdf). (Accessed 28 Sept. 2024)
9. Kumra, Savita, and Susan Vinnicombe. (2008). *A Study of the Promotion to Partner Process in a Professional Services Firm: How Women Are Disadvantaged*. British

- Journal of Management*, vol. 19, no. S1, pp. S65-S74, doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8551.2008.00572.x (Accessed 28 Sept. 2024).
10. Heilman, Madeline E. (2012). *Description and Prescription: How Gender Stereotypes Prevent Women's Ascent up the Organizational Ladder*. *Journal of Social Issues*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 657-674, doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00234. Accessed 28 Sept. 2024.
 11. Singh, Parbudyal. (2012). *Balancing Work and Life: Implications for Indian Women Professionals*. *Journal of Management Development*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 258-271, doi.org/10.1108/02621711211199429. Accessed 28 Sept. 2024.
 12. Ibarra, Herminia, Nancy M. Carter, and Christine Silva. *Why Men Still Get More Promotions Than Women*. *Harvard Business Review*, Sept. 2010, hbr.org/2010/09/why-men-still-get-more-promotions-than-women. Accessed 28 Sept. 2024
 13. Rudman, Laurie A., and Peter Glick. (2001). *Prescriptive Gender Stereotypes and Backlash toward Agentic Women*. *Journal of Social Issues*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 743-762, doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00239. Accessed 28 Sept. 2024.
 14. Korkmaz, E., van Engen, M., Knappert, L., & Schalk, R. (2022). *Inclusive leadership and employee outcomes: The mediating role of perceived insider status*. *Journal of Management & Organization*. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-management-and-organization/article/power-of-inclusive-leadership-exploring-the-mediating-role-of-identityrelated-processes-and-conditional-effects-of-synergy-diversity-climate-in-nurturing-positive-employee-behaviors>
 15. Sabharwal, M., Levine, H., & D'Agostino, M. J. (2018). *Public Managers' Role in Creating Inclusive Work Environments*. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.837821/full>
 16. Shore, L. M., Cleveland, J. N., & Sanchez, D. (2018). *Inclusive leadership and organizational outcomes*. Available at: [https://routledgeopenresearch.org/articles/2-16\(Routledge Open Research\)](https://routledgeopenresearch.org/articles/2-16(Routledge Open Research)).
 17. Jing, J., Ding, T., & Liu, S. (2022). *Leadership, Diversity, and Inclusion in Organizations*. *Frontiers Research Topic*. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/8395/leadership-diversity-and-inclusion-in-organization>
 18. McKinsey & Company. (2023). *Women in the workplace 2024: 10th anniversary report*. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com>
 19. Skyline G. (2023). *Women in leadership 2023: The challenges, benefits & development of female leadership in the workplace*. Retrieved from <https://skylineg.com>
 20. World Economic Forum. (2023). *12 top leaders share how to achieve inclusive leadership*. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org>
 21. Yin, W., & Liu, S. (2022). *The Relationship between Empowering Leadership and Radical Creativity*. Available at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.01234/full>

Online Resources

1. <https://www.thehindu.com/business/Industry/proportion-of-women-in-leadership-roles-stagnating-in-india-linkedin-report/article68232305.ece>